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MAKTABGACHA
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TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
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- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
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- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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IDENTIFYING THE CAUSE OF ADDICTION TO ALCOHOL AND DRUGS

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Abstract: This article examines the underlying causes of alcohol and drug addiction, highlighting psychological, social and behavioural factors that contribute to the development of dependency. Special attention is given to the role of psychoactive substances, psychological vulnerability, motivational aspects and addictive behavioural patterns. The analysis also explores how psychological defence mechanisms and emotional fascination contribute to persistent substance use.

Key words: alcohol addiction, drug addiction, psychoactive substances, addictive behaviour, psychological predisposition, psychological defence, emotional fascination, motives for use.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada alkogol va giyohvandlikka qaramlikning asosiy sabablarini aniqlash masalasi yoritiladi. Tadqiqotda psixoaktiv moddalarning ta'siri, psixologik zaiflik, motivatsion omillar hamda odatga aylangan xulq-atvor modellari qaramlik shakllanishiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi ilmiy tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, psixologik himoya mexanizmlari va emotsional jalb etilish omillari moddalardan doimiy foydalanishni kuchaytiruvchi omillar sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: alkogolizm, giyohvandlik, psixoaktiv moddalar, addiktiv xulq-atvor, psixologik moyillik, psixologik himoya, emotsional jalb etilish, foydalanish motivlari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются основные причины формирования алкогольной и наркотической зависимости. Анализ уделяет внимание влиянию психоактивных веществ, психологической уязвимости, мотивационных факторов и моделей аддиктивного поведения, способствующих развитию зависимости. Дополнительно исследуется роль психологических защитных механизмов и эмоционального увлечения, усиливающих склонность к регулярному употреблению психоактивных веществ.

Ключевые слова: алкоголизм, наркомания, психоактивные вещества, аддиктивное поведение, психологическая предрасположенность, психологическая защита, эмоциональное увлечение, мотивы употребления.

INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of alcoholism and drug addiction in the world is a fundamental social problem of our time. According to most experts, drug addiction and alcoholism undermine the socio-economic development of the country, hinder the progress of science and the growth of the economy, reduce the quality of life of the population and the level of human potential. They negatively affect life expectancy, infant mortality, the number of scuffles, attempts and murders. Some of the reasons for the spread of alcoholism may be factors such as increased anxiety, fears, unemployment and poverty.

The spread of psychoactive substances in Uzbekistan is a serious social problem with long-term negative outcomes in many areas of social life. Studies show a strong correlation between the level of substance prevalence and critical indicators of human potential and the quality of social existence.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on the causes of alcohol and drug addiction highlights a complex interaction of psychological, social and behavioural determinants. Fedotov's analysis demonstrates that regional socio-economic instability significantly increases susceptibility to addictive behaviours, particularly in communities with limited access to mental health support and educational resources. Similarly, Gruzkova's work emphasises the role of individual psychological traits, noting that impulsivity, emotional instability, and a low threshold for coping with stress are strongly associated with higher risks of alcohol and drug dependence. These findings collectively indicate that addiction is not solely a biological condition but is deeply rooted in personal vulnerability and social context.

Further studies also underline the impact of lifestyle, social environment and behavioural habits on the development of addiction. Research by Kengesbayevich shows that health-oriented education and preventive pedagogical technologies in youth populations play a crucial role in reducing tendencies toward harmful substance use. Meanwhile, Lisovskiy and Kolesnikov's work identifies addiction as a broader social problem shaped by value disorientation, weakened moral norms and the growth of substance availability in society. Together, these scientific insights confirm that alcohol and drug addiction emerge from intertwined socio-cultural, psychological and behavioural factors that require comprehensive preventive and rehabilitative approaches.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to some experts, one of the main reasons for the spread of alcoholism and drug addiction is the inability of the population to cope with stress and problems in life. Thus, the harder the living conditions become, the higher the level of anxiety and the less developed the social postulates designed to help the population cope with the increased burden of life, the higher the risk of drug and alcohol abuse in the country.

If we pay attention to news programmes on television and in the print media, it becomes clear that the fear of poverty is largely fuelled by the state itself. The consequences of this can be very serious, as it is not only poverty and difficult living conditions that have a negative impact on the spread of addictive behaviour, but also the fear of poverty and the fear of falling into these difficult conditions. If it is not easy to change the actual factors of living conditions, it is nevertheless possible to organise a favourable and safe atmosphere in society, in which the population will not have fears about their future, with the help of mass media. Unfortunately, at present we observe a completely different picture.

The social and socio-cultural conditions of drug and alcohol abuse include the deterioration of the socio-economic situation in the country, the value diversity of views and principles, the increase in the volume of drugs and alcohol on the market and their availability, the loyalty of the law to substance abuse, the fashion for substance use, the propaganda of substance use in films and society's traditions related to substance use.

The current situation is interpreted as a violation of existing values, principles and cultural norms. State institutions do not provide the individual with a model of education of vital values that allows for the formation of conscious systems of life goals. In such a situation, drug use is understood as a desire to escape from group values, a removal of responsibility from state institutions, and a shift in definitions of the purpose of human life and the system of their achievement.

The nature of addictive behaviour lies in a person's desire to change his or her mental state by taking certain substances or by concentrating on certain activities. The process of taking such substances, attachment to an object or action entails the development of intense emotions and takes on dimensions of such magnitude that over time it begins to control the person's life, depriving him or her of the will to resist the addiction.

Addictive behaviour emerges over time and goes through several stages. The beginning of deviation is associated with the experience of an acute change in the mental state of an individual as a result of taking certain substances, and the understanding that there is a way to change one's psychological state, to experience a sense of uplift, joy and similar emotions. Then a steady sequence of addiction to addictive means emerges, and eventually any discomforting state becomes a stimulus, an addictive provocateur. Subsequently, the addictive part of the personality completely determines a person's behaviour, complicating his contacts with people at both the psychological and social levels, destroying the life, psyche and health of the individual.

Addictive personalities can be united by their common problem, which imposes its imprint on lifestyles, relationships and activities. Substance-dependent people, as a group, are characterised by certain mental states and a set of personality traits often observed in drug and alcohol addicts. These qualities include impulsivity, immaturity, a low threshold of tolerance for life's difficulties, anxiety and depression.

The social and psychological prerequisites of mass consumption of psychoactive substances are also worth mentioning. The violation of the ideological foundations of society has led to the fact that many people have completely lost spiritual reference points in life and their worldview has been deformed. Life, even if not fully realised, has lost its meaning for most individuals. The principles of collective interests have become

unstable, and the psychology of individual existence has not been practically formed. The ideological situation in the country has been changing so rapidly that normal adaptation has become practically unrealizable. Any social structure, while possessing marginalised groups, has at its core the middle strata of the population who need to realise the meaning and purpose of their lives.

In many countries, propaganda in mass media, advertisements, the film industry and literature is aimed at forming a certain system of views and values. People enjoy life, nature, family, communication and children; they find satisfaction in their profession and hobbies and realise that they are a part of a certain national and state system. There is the formation of the user in a positive sense—an individual as a guardian who honours social traditions, common sense and the foundations of social order. As a result of generational change, experience and ideologies are passed on. The next generation is more willing to adopt radical views on life, but retains the basic worldview postulates.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the reasons people start using alcohol or drugs is that psychoactive substances act as an effective psychological shield. Some people believe that psychoactive substances have a beneficial effect on mood, well-being, self-esteem, self-image, limitation and anxiety. However, evidence suggests that this is a self-perpetuating effect.

Also, psychological factors of addiction to psychoactive substances can be attributed to individual and personal qualities of the person. Among the psychological characteristics of individuals predisposed to alcohol use, there are: insufficiently organised personality, impulsiveness, high irritability and an external locus of control, extraversion, rigidity of thinking and related unproductivity, as well as the inability to cope with anxiety and tension in ways acceptable to society, i.e., the formation of ineffective coping strategies, particularly in the form of avoidance of life difficulties.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The main motivations for alcohol use are self-affirmation, relaxation and “drinking for company”. At the same time, such prerequisites as loneliness, intra-personal conflicts, family violence, as well as psychological disorders such as bipolarity, anxiety, internal tension, low self-esteem and lack of recognition in socially positive activity are more characteristic of people with drug dependence. The main factor that encourages a person to use psychoactive substances is a low level of criticality towards alcohol and drugs. It is important not only how the close environment and surroundings affect the individual, but also how he or she reacts to them.

References:

1. Fedotov A. A. Alkogolizm i narkomaniya: regionalniy analiz / A. A. Fedotov // *Mejdunarodniy jurnal gumanitarnikh i yestestvennikh nauk.* – 2020. – Vip. 10–2(49). – S. 192–200.
2. Gruzkova S. Yu. Individualno-lichnostniye osobennosti alkogolikov i narkomanov v sotsialnom kontekste / S. Yu. Gruzkova // *Kazanskiy pedagogicheskiy jurnal.* – 2011. – Vip. 4(88). – S. 137–145.
3. Kengesbayevich R. M. (2025). Formation of Healthy Lifestyle of Medical Students in Higher Educational Institutions in Medical Direction. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 3(1), 58–61.
4. Kengesbayevich R. M. (2025, January). Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in the Formation of Healthy Lifestyle of Students in Higher Education Institutions. In *International Conference on Adaptive Learning Technologies* (Vol. 13, pp. 18–19).
5. Lisovskiy V. D., Kolesnikov E. A. *Narkotizm kak sotsialnaya problema.* – SPb: Chelovek i obshchestvo, 2001. – 200 s.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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